

REINFORCING

Responsible tErritories and Institutions eNable and Foster Open
Research and inClusive Innovation for traNsitions Governance

D.4.2 – [REINFORCING cascading grants supporting Documents - Guide for applicants]

Grant Agreement Number: 101094435
Project Acronym: REINFORCING

Due date: 31/10/2023

Actual date: 30/11/2023

Document author/s: [ITB]

Version: 1.1

Dissemination level: [PU]

Status: Draft (*the document as it stands can be considered as fairly definitive; nevertheless, it may be subject to slight changes based on applicants' feedback*)

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Document History			
Version	Date	Comments	Author
1.1	30/11/2023	First version of D4.2	ITB

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Page

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1. INTRODUCTION.....	8
1.1 REINFORCING project	8
1.2 REINFORCING partners	8
1.3 Target audience	10
2. REINFORCING’S OPEN CALL.....	11
2.1 Aim of the call	11
2.2 Type of grants.....	11
2.3 Grants timeline	12
2.4 Eligibility conditions	13
2.5 General criteria	13
2.6 Requirements for implementation	13
3. APPLICATION	15
3.1 How to apply.....	15
3.2 Where to apply	15
4. EVALUATION AND SELECTION PROCESS.....	16
4.1 Evaluation process	16
4.2 Evaluation criteria.....	17
4.3 Scoring system.....	17
4.4 Disclaimer on the selection process.....	17
5. GRANTS CONTRACTING AND PAYMENT OF THE FUNDS.....	18
5.1 Contractual arrangements and general payment terms	18
5.2 Reporting and payment of the funds	20
5.3 Eligible costs.....	21
6. CONFIDENTIALITY AND DATA PROTECTION	22
7. DISCLAIMER	23
8. SUPPORT TO APPLICANTS.....	24
ANNEX 1 – ORRI BOOSTER TEMPLATE	25
ANNEX 2 – ORRI INCUBATOR TEMPLATE	31
ANNEX 3 – DECLARATION OF HONOUR	37
ANNEX 4 – FREQUENTLY ASKED QUESTIONS	40

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ORRI Open and Responsible Research and Innovation.

RRI Responsible Research and Innovation.

ERA European Research Area.

HEU Horizon Europe.

FSTP Financial support to third parties.

FGB Fondazione Bassetti (the Project Coordinator)

ITB Consorzio Italbiotec (the Contracting Entity)

B1 ORRI Booster call 1

I1 ORRI Incubator call 1

CSO Civil Society Organizations.

NGO Non-Governmental Organizations

SME Small and Medium Enterprises

GDPR General Data Protection Regulation

OSS One-Stop Source

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The primary objective of *Deliverable 4.2 - REINFORCING cascading grants supporting Documents - Guide for applicants* is to provide comprehensive guidelines for applicants seeking financial support from REINFORCING, through the submission of proposals for cascading grants. Below, the main key point of the REINFORCING cascading grants are briefly summarized:

1. Grant Calls:

- 2 types of grants: ORRI boosters (small) grants for applicants already experienced in ORRI that would like to strengthen and institutionalize their ORRI approach and ORRI incubators (large) grants for consortia of newcomers to RRI.
- Total call budget: 24M€ (48% of the REINFORCING budget).
- Max grant amount: 20.000 € for ORRI booster (small) grants and 60.000€ for ORRI incubator (large) grants.

2. Application Process:

- Applications will be submitted electronically via the REINFORCING website (<https://www.reinforcing.eu/>) by filling out an online form (requiring general information) and uploading mandatory template: technical proposal (Annexes 1 and 2) and Declaration of Honour (DoH, Annex 3).
- Specific application templates for ORRI Booster (Annex 1) and ORRI Incubator (Annex 2) grants are foreseen.

3. Evaluation and Selection Process:

- The evaluation process will be based on three steps: eligibility check and formal requirements carried out by the contracting entity, preliminary assessment by the consortium, final evaluation carried out by three external evaluators.
- Evaluation criteria: Objectives, need and approach (Excellence), Changes to be achieved (Impact), and Activities (Implementation).

4. Contracting and Funding:

- Contractual obligations include confidentiality, ethics, gender equality, EU funding visibility, and IPR.
- Each grantee will be asked to complete a Progress Report, including justifications of expenses, precise descriptions of the actions implemented, the problems encountered, and the solutions adopted. One and two Progress Reports will be required for ORRI booster grants and for ORRI incubator grants, respectively.
- Payment scheme and timeline vary for ORRI booster and incubator grants.

5. Eligible Costs:

- Personnel costs, purchase costs (materials and travel costs, the last ones for ORRI Incubators only), and indirect costs (25% flat rate of eligible direct costs).

6. Additional annexes:

- Annex 1 and 2: Technical proposal templates (different templates for ORRI Booster and ORRI Incubator grants)
- Annex 3: Declaration of Honour template
- Annex 4: Frequently Asked Questions

[D4.2-[REINFORCING cascading grants supporting Documents - Guidelines for applicants]]

The current document and related annexes are complete and final. However, the consortium may slightly modify them during the project duration based on the feedback of applicants and grantees.

REINFORCING PROJECT

Project Acronym	REINFORCING
Project Title	Responsible tEerritories and Institutions eNable and Foster Open Research and inClusive Innovation for traNsitions Governance
Project Number	101094435
Project Topic	HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-40
Project Duration	50 months (1/01/2023 – 28/02/2027)
Overall Budget	€ 5.000.082,50
Reserved budget for cascading grants	€ 2.400.000,00

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 REINFORCING project

REINFORCING supports organizations and institutions in Europe to transition to a new paradigm where responsibility and openness drive research and innovation processes. In the current situation, the green and digital transitions have become an urgency that can no longer wait. The twin transition, as they have come to be known, will bring enormous benefits but also undesired externalities. Making it fair and inclusive is therefore key. To succeed, institutions and territories need to shift to more open and transparent R&I practices in which all actors share responsibility to develop services and products that are acceptable, sustainable and bring social satisfaction.

The Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (ORRI) approach promotes collaborative efforts. From sharing research outputs as early as possible to engaging citizens in co-creation processes, R&I should be open to the whole society.

Implementing Open and Responsible R&I can seem a daunting task. However, over the past decade, many resources and tools have been created, but an effort to systematize, curate and create a single entry point was still missing. REINFORCING is this much-needed European central hub for Open and Responsible R&I. The project's platform is the entry point to knowledge, training, ORRI skills match-making and capacity building for organizations interested in starting or continuing their journey to creating an inclusive R&I ecosystem. Furthermore, the project brokers unique networking opportunities for organizations, institutions and territories interested in becoming part of the European ecosystem that is transforming the R&I system by bringing it closer to society and societal needs.

To support this change, REINFORCING has ring-fenced funding for 96 grants - between 20,000 and 60,000 euros- to invite institutions from around Europe to develop projects aiming at implementing new modes of doing R&I that drive more just transitions. The project will launch 7 open calls for cascading grants to help territories and organizations experimenting with ORRI for the first time (ORRI Incubator Open Calls) or to boost those scaling up their ORRI activities (ORRI Booster Open Calls).

1.2 REINFORCING partners

	<p>FONDAZIONE GIANNINO BASSETTI ITALY https://www.fondazionebassetti.org/</p>
	<p>AIT AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY GMBH AUSTRIA https://www.ait.ac.at/en/</p>
	<p>TEKNOLOGIAN TUTKIMUSKESKUS VTT OY FINLAND https://www.vttresearch.com/en</p>

	<p>FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG EV</p> <p>GERMANY</p> <p>https://www.fraunhofer.de/</p>
	<p>FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION</p> <p>SPAIN</p> <p>https://www.tecnalia.com/en/</p>
	<p>CONSORZIO ITALBIOTEC</p> <p>ITALY</p> <p>https://www.italbiotec.it/</p>
	<p>STICKYDOT SRL</p> <p>BELGIUM</p> <p>https://stickydot.eu/</p>
	<p>INMARK EUROPA SA</p> <p>SPAIN</p> <p>https://www.grupoinmark.com/</p>
	<p>EUROPEAN BUSINESS AND INNOVATION CENTRE NETWORK AISBL</p> <p>BELGIUM</p> <p>https://ebn.eu/</p>
	<p>RHEINISCH-WESTFAELISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE AACHEN</p> <p>GERMANY</p> <p>https://www.rwth-aachen.de/</p>

	<p>UNIVERZITET U NOVOM SADU FAKULTET TEHNICKIH NAUKA</p> <p>SERBIA</p> <p>http://ftn.uns.ac.rs/n1386094394/faculty-of-technical-sciences</p>
<p>POLJOPRIVREDNI FAKULTET UNIVERZITET U NOVOM SADU</p>	<p>UNIVERZITET U NOVOM SADU, POLJOPRIVREDNI FAKULTET NOVI SAD</p> <p>SERBIA</p> <p>http://polj.uns.ac.rs/</p>
<p>UNIVERSITY OF NOVI SAD FACULTY OF TECHNOLOGY NOVI SAD</p>	<p>TEHNOLOSKI FAKULTET NOVI SAD</p> <p>SERBIA</p> <p>https://www.tf.uns.ac.rs/</p>

Table 1: REINFORCING partners

1.3 REINFORCING Grants targeted audience

The REINFORCING cascading grants calls will address the following legal entities (but not limited to):

- Higher education institutions
- Civil Society Organizations (CSOs)
- Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs)
- Research Centers
- Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs).

1. REINFORCING'S OPEN CALLS

2.1 Aim of the calls

A big part of REINFORCING efforts (also budget-wise) will be dedicated to shaping and handling cascading grants open calls, in close dialogue with the EC, through 7 open calls, differentiated by the level of ORRI maturity of the applicants. REINFORCING grants will be awarded to projects planning to implement ORRI implementation activities.

All REINFORCING calls will adhere to EU principles of transparency, equal treatment, conflict of interest, and confidentiality, ensuring an objective and clear selection procedure.

4 smaller scale calls, called ORRI boosters, will select and support institutions already experienced in ORRI that would like to further enhance its uptake and its various dimensions. 3 larger grants, called ORRI incubators, will support more complex initiatives lasting one year and engage at least two different "newcomers" institutions implementing ORRI actions together.

Beneficiaries will benefit from REINFORCING support and services, including training modules on ORRI principles and practices. Beneficiaries will be requested to take part in peer-learning activities (at the midterm of their interventions), to showcase the results and impact of their actions, and to join online REINFORCING webinars. REINFORCING Impact prizes will be awarded to the most successful ORRI Incubators grantees, announced during public events involving policymakers. Incubator grantees will also receive mentoring support at the end of their journey to foster long-term ORRI sustainability and institutionalization.

2.2 Type of grants

Two kinds of grants will be delivered by REINFORCING: ORRI booster (small) grants and ORRI incubators (large) grants. The specific objectives and targets of the calls will be defined throughout the duration of the project.

2.2.1 ORRI Booster grants (small grants)

Small grants, also called ORRI boosters, will be awarded to applicants (at least one beneficiary) already experienced in ORRI that would like to strengthen and institutionalize their ORRI approach. Each ORRI booster call will support 12 proposals implementing an 8-month project. The maximum amount granted for each project is 20,000 €.

Grant	Duration (months)	Estimated number of grants	Estimated number of calls
ORRI booster grants	8	48	4

Table 2: Small grants key features

2.2.2 ORRI Incubator grants (large grants)

Large grants, also called ORRI incubators, will be awarded to consortia of beneficiaries (at least two beneficiaries per consortium) that are newcomers in ORRI and that would like to embark on an ORRI approach. Each ORRI incubators call will support 8 consortia implementing a 12-month project. The maximum amount granted for each project is 60,000 €

Grant	Duration (months)	Estimated number of grants	Estimated number of calls
ORRI incubator grants	12	24	3

Table 3: Large grants key features

2.3 Grants timeline

Starting from November 2023, REINFORCING calls will be launched every 4 months alternating between the two types of grants – ORRI booster and ORRI incubators.

ORRI Boosters will be launched in:

- B1: November 2023
- B2: November 2024
- B3: March 2025
- B4: November 2025

ORRI Incubators will be launched in:

- I1: March 2024
- I2: July 2024
- I3: July 2025

Each call, after the launch, will be open for two months, as visible in Table 4.

<u>Call closing</u>	2 months after the launch. Specific Call closing date will be reported for each call.
<u>Evaluation process</u>	Starting after the call closing and going on for one month
<u>Publication of the results</u>	One month after the call closing
<u>Contracting phase</u>	The contracting phase will last for about one month and will be closed two months after the call closing
<u>Project start</u>	The projects are expected to start in the 5 th month after the call launch date and will last for 8 months in case of ORRI Booster and 12 months in case of ORRI incubators

Table 4: Cascading grants calls general timeline.

As an example, the timeline for the first ORRI Booster and Incubator calls is provided below:

Figure 1: Calls timeline – Gantt Diagram of B1 and I1 calls

2.4 Eligibility conditions

Proposals will be considered eligible and enter the evaluation phase if each and all following conditions are met. Only complete applications will be taken into account by the reviewing committee.

- Applicants must be established in an EU country (Member State or associated country), including their outermost regions or associated countries eligible to receive HEU grants, provided that the applicants are not covered by the Council sanctions in force.
- Applicants must be legal entities such as, but not limited to, Civil Society Organizations (CSO), Non-Governmental Organizations (NGO), Higher Education Institutions, Research Centres and Small and Medium Enterprises (SME).
- Applicants must declare their financial stability.
- Applicants shall not have any potential conflict of interest with the REINFORCING selection process (notably they should not have legal relationship with any organization that is a member of the REINFORCING consortium, including affiliated entities, or any person sitting on the advisory board).

Eligibility criteria will apply individually to each consortium participant.

2.5 General criteria

Besides eligibility criteria, REINFORCING applicants must meet the following general criteria:

- Activities must focus on the actions described in the call conditions.
- Applications must be completed in all its parts (administrative and technical part) and must be written in English (applications partially written in another language are not eligible).
- Applicants must submit their application via the project website (<https://www.reinforcing.eu/>) using the templates provided (Annexes 1 and 2). Applications submitted by other means will not be evaluated.
- It is not possible to submit multiple applications under the same call. However, applicants can apply for more than one REINFORCING call as long as the funding amount received by the same organization doesn't exceed €60 000.
- Applicants must declare that the same project hasn't received funding under another call.

2.6 Requirements for the implementation

In order to positively contribute to the REINFORCING objectives, grantees are requested to carry out the following activities during the implementation:

- Deliver at least one ORRI tool to be included in the REINFORCING platform.
- Contribute to update the REINFORCING project website with grantees' achievements and information;
- Attend and contribute to a final webinar in which they will be asked to present their results;
- Participate in a mid-term review meeting aimed to assess the impact of the grants on beneficiaries;
- (*Only for ORRI Incubators*) Beneficiary of ORRI Incubator Grants must attend preliminary training activities at the beginning of their activities to familiarize them with ORRI principles. Training will last one day and a half and will be delivered on-site in Brussels. Costs related to training (personnel and travel) can be funded by the grant (thus, included in the budget overview).
- (*Suggested but not mandatory*) Online communication (webpage on partners' website; social media communication on already existing social media channels).

3 APPLICATION

3.1 How to apply?

ORRI booster and ORRI incubator calls will be published according to the timeline provided in paragraph 2.3 on the [Funding & Tenders portal](#) and on the project channels (project website, REINFORCING LinkedIn account).

The application form will consist of three parts:

- An online form requiring general information on the project to be completed on the REINFORCING [website](#) for each applicant;
- Technical proposal with the description of the project, using the mandatory template (Annexes 1 and 2 according to the type of grants), including the detailed description on how the grant will be used. The completed template must be uploaded on the online form;
- A Declaration of Honour (Annex 3) that must be signed by all project partners. Only complete applications will be considered for selection/evaluation.

ORRI booster and ORRI incubator proposals will be based on two different application forms that can be downloaded from the project website:

- ORRI Booster template (Annex 1)
- ORRI Incubator template (Annex 2)

3.2 Where to apply?

All proposals will be submitted electronically via the REINFORCING project website (<https://www.reinforcing.eu/>).

Proposals must be received by the Call closing date and time. Late proposals, or proposals submitted by any means other than those indicated in the Guide for applicants, will not be considered.

All proposals and related data, knowledge and documents will be treated according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016).

4 EVALUATION AND SELECTION PROCESS

4.1 Evaluation process

The evaluation and ranking of applications will be based on a set of criteria in addition to the above-mentioned eligibility conditions. The evaluation process is structured as follows:

4.1.1 Eligibility check and formal requirements

The REINFORCING consortium, and namely Consorzio Italbitoe (ITB) as the contracting entity, will check each proposal for formal requirements, including:

- Compliance with eligibility criteria as defined in paragraph 2.2 Eligibility criteria.
- Completeness of the requested administrative, financial and technical information.
- Language of the application (English is mandatory).
- Compliance with the submission process and deadline.

Applications that do not meet one or more mandatory requirements will be excluded from the selection phase. All applicants eliminated from the process after the eligibility check will be notified by email.

4.1.2 Preliminary assessment by the consortium

If eligible and complete, the REINFORCING consortium will proceed with a first assessment of the proposals. The resulting proposals will then be evaluated and ranked by external panelists. The preliminary quality criteria will focus on the Excellence and Impact section and in particular on the compliance of the proposals with the call objectives.

The preliminary assessment will result in the selection of a maximum of 48 proposals for each ORRI booster call and 48 proposals for each ORRI incubator call. All applicants eliminated from the process after the preliminary assessment will be notified by email at the end of the call evaluation process.

4.1.3 Final evaluation

Each proposal that passes the preliminary assessment will be evaluated by three external evaluators according to the awarding criteria as defined in paragraph 5.3. Evaluators for each call are selected through an open call to ensure the best possible expertise in the evaluation process and the absence of conflicts of interest. Experts who are involved in a proposal are, indeed, not eligible to review any of the proposals submitted under the same call. Evaluation panel members are furthermore bound to a confidentiality agreement with the contracting entity.

The evaluation process will consist of an initial individual evaluation, carried out individually by each expert of the evaluation panel, and an online panel assessment, where experts reach an agreement on the proposal evaluation. As a general rule, the proposals submitted under the same call will be evaluated by the same panel of evaluators.

The proposals obtaining the highest ranking after the final evaluation will be selected. All applicants undergoing the final evaluation will be informed of the evaluation ranking and results by receiving an Evaluation Summary Report.

4.2 Evaluation criteria

The proposals selected for funding must demonstrate high quality in the context and in specific criteria set out for each call. Evaluation criteria evaluated by the external panelists

[D4.2-[REINFORCING cascading grants supporting Documents - Guidelines for applicants]]

will take into consideration all three sections described in paragraph 3.1. The evaluation criteria are described in the table below.

Section	Evaluation criteria
Objectives, needs and approach [Excellence]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarity of the project's objectives. • Pertinence of the project's objectives with the call requirements.
Changes to be achieved [Impact]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expected changes benefitting the organization(s) involved, the territory and society at large
Activities [Implementation]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality and consistency of the actions in relation to the project objectives.

Table 5: Evaluation criteria for proposals assessment

4.3 Scoring system

For the evaluation, each section will be scored from 0 to 5 as follows:

- 0: not acceptable;
- 1 Poor: The criteria in the section are addressed in an inadequate manner, or there are serious inherent weaknesses;
- 2 Fair: While the proposal broadly addresses the criteria in the section, there are significant weaknesses;
- 3 Good: The proposal addresses the criteria in the section well, although improvements would be necessary;
- 4 Very good: The proposal addresses the criteria in the section very well, although certain improvements are still possible;
- 5 Excellent: The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the section. Any shortcomings are minor.

The average for each section will be calculated from all reviewer evaluations. The average of all reviewer evaluations for a particular section has to be at least 3. If a criterion is rated on average below 3, the application will be excluded from funding immediately. The sum of these averaged scores results in the total evaluation score for each project. Thus, the highest achievable total evaluation score is 15. The minimum total evaluation score for a project to be funded is 9.

Proposals obtaining a score of 9 or more will be ranked and the proposals with the highest ranking will be selected until funds for the call are exhausted.

Diversity, Equity and Inclusion will be considered as ranking criteria for ex-equo proposals.

In some cases, diversity could be the leading principle driving the selection of the projects, aiming to obtain a balanced list of selected projects, in terms of geography, types of stakeholders involved, issues addressed and gender.

4.4 Disclaimer on the selection process

All submitted proposals will be treated equally: they will be evaluated impartially based on their merits, irrespective of their origin or the identity of the applicants.

The evaluation procedure will be clear and transparent for applicants; the evaluation ranking and results will be made available to each applicant through an Evaluation Summary Report and released on the REINFORCING website. REINFORCING will publish the outcome of the calls without delay, including a description of grantees' projects, the date of the award, the duration, and the legal name and country of the beneficiary (or beneficiaries).

5 GRANTS CONTRACTING AND PAYMENT OF THE FUNDS

5.1 Contractual arrangements and general payment terms

Once the evaluation process is concluded, each selected proposal will be invited to sign the REINFORCING Sub-Grant Agreement with the Consortium (represented by Consorzio Italbiotec for the purposes of signature).

The funds awarded under the REINFORCING Sub-Grant Agreement are provided directly from the funds of the Horizon Europe-funded project, and are, therefore, funds owned by the European Commission. Management of the REINFORCING funds has been transferred to the project partners via Grant Agreement Number 101094435 signed with the European Commission.

All beneficiaries of REINFORCING financial support must comply with contractual obligations including:

- **Avoiding conflicts of interest:** The beneficiaries must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the Sub-Grant Agreement could be compromised for reasons involving family, emotional life, political or national affinity, economic interest or any other direct or indirect interest ('conflict of interests').
- **Confidentiality obligations:** The parties must keep confidential any data, documents or other material (in any form) that is identified as sensitive in writing ('sensitive information') - during the implementation of the action and for at least the time limit of 5 years after the final payment. If a beneficiary requests, the REINFORCING Consortium may agree to keep such information confidential for a longer period. Unless otherwise agreed between the parties, they may use sensitive information only to implement the Sub-Grant Agreement. The REINFORCING Consortium may disclose sensitive information to its staff and to other EU institutions and bodies. It may moreover disclose sensitive information, if:
 - a) this is necessary to implement the Sub-Grant Agreement or safeguard the EU financial interests.
 - b) the recipients of the information are bound by an obligation of confidentiality.

The confidentiality obligations no longer apply if:

- a) the disclosing party agrees to release the other party.
 - b) the information becomes publicly available, without breaching any confidentiality obligation.
 - c) the disclosure of the sensitive information is required by EU, international or national law.
- **Handling of classified information:** The parties must handle classified information in accordance with the applicable EU, international or national law on classified information (in particular, Decision 2015/44417 and its implementing rules). Deliverables which contain classified information must be submitted according to special procedures agreed with the contracting entity. Action tasks involving classified information may be subcontracted only after explicit approval (in writing) from the contracting entity. Classified information may not be disclosed to any third party (including participants involved in the action implementation) without prior explicit written approval from the contracting entity.

- **Ethics:** The granted action must be carried out in line with the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles.
- **Ensuring gender equality:** Applicants are invited to take all measures to promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of the action. They must aim for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including supervisory and managerial levels to the extent possible.
- **Give visibility to the EU funding:** Unless otherwise agreed with the contracting entity, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos. Furthermore, for dissemination and use of results generated through the financial support from the Consortium, the recipients must credit the REINFORCING project through proper citation and appearance of the REINFORCING logo and EU Logo, including the proper citation "This project has received funding from the European Research Executive Agency (REA), under grant agreement number 101094435".

- **Ensuring Intellectual Property Rights:** The ownership of IPR created by the beneficiaries using the REINFORCING funding will remain with the beneficiaries, who will be the sole owners of the solutions in any form of IP created within the framework of their funded projects. The beneficiaries are advised to arrange for internal contracts regarding Intellectual Property Rights, and the use and dissemination of the results generated by the project teams through the funding obtained via REINFORCING financial support.
- **Providing additional information without any delays:** the beneficiaries must provide during the action or afterwards any information requested in order to verify the eligibility of the costs or contributions declared, proper implementation of the action and compliance with the other obligations under the Sub-Grant Agreement. The information provided must be accurate, precise and complete and in the format requested, including electronic format.
- **Keeping the data updated:** The beneficiaries must keep — at all times, during the action or afterwards — their information stored in by the REINFORCING Consortium up to date, in particular, their name, address, legal representatives, legal form and organization type.
- **Communicating information about events and circumstances which impact the action:** The beneficiaries must immediately inform the contracting entity (and the other beneficiaries) of any of the following:
 - a) events which are likely to affect or delay the implementation of the action or affect the EU's financial interests, and in particular changes in their legal,

financial, technical, organisational or ownership situation (including changes linked to one of the exclusion grounds listed in the declaration of honour signed before grant signature)

- b)** circumstances affecting the decision to award the grant or compliance with requirements under the Agreement.
- **Record-keeping and supporting documents:** The beneficiaries must — at least for 3 years after final payment — keep records and other supporting documents to prove the proper implementation of the action in line with the accepted standards in the respective field (if any). In addition, the beneficiaries must keep adequate records and supporting documents to prove that their cost accounting practices have been applied in a consistent manner, based on objective criteria, regardless of the source of funding, and that they comply with the eligibility conditions.

5.1.1 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations linked to carrying out the action, the grant may be reduced.

5.2 Reporting and payment of the funds

Each grantee will be asked to complete a Progress Report, including justifications of expenses, precise descriptions of the actions implemented, the problems encountered, and the solutions adopted. These reports will allow monitoring of the grants, checking that funds are being used according to the plan and, at the same time, collecting information on the impact of REINFORCING grants. A template will be provided and made available to all beneficiaries.

For ORRI booster grants, a single final progress report will be required, while for ORRI incubator grants two progress reports will be required (mid-term and final report) because of the longer duration of the pilot projects.

Payment of the funds will be made at the beginning of the project and concurrently to the validation of Progress Reports. This distribution will avoid misuse of funds.

Type	Payment scheme
<u>ORRI booster grants</u>	50% at the beginning of the project; 50% at the end
<u>ORRI incubator grants</u>	40% at the beginning of the project; 30% after mid-term progress report validation; 30% at the end of the project

Table 6: Financing terms per grant category

For ORRI incubator projects that involve more than one institution, the payment will be made to the institution appointed as coordinator. The coordinator will be responsible for distributing the payments between the beneficiaries without unjustified delay.

5.3 Eligible costs

For general eligibility costs, please see article 6 of the Horizon Europe AGA (V1.0 DRAFT – 01.04-2023).

Eligible costs include:

- Personnel costs as described in Article in 6.2.A of the Horizon Europe AGA.
- Purchase costs include:
 - Travel, accommodation and subsistence (see Article 6.2.C.1 of the Horizon Europe AGA) (*these costs are eligible for ORRI Incubators – large grants only*)
 - Other goods, works or services, if necessary to implement the action (see Article 6.2.C.3 of the Horizon Europe AGA).
- Indirect costs are costs that cannot be identified as specific costs directly linked to the performance of the action. They are calculated as a 25% flat rate of the eligible direct costs (personnel costs and purchase costs).

6 CONFIDENTIALITY AND DATA PROTECTION

GDPR compliance: The General Data Protection Regulation (2016/679/EU) guarantees that the processing of data is carried out in compliance with the fundamental rights and freedoms, as well as the dignity of the data subject with particular reference to confidentiality, personal identity and the right to data protection.

By applying, the applicant agrees to the storage and use of their personal data for the execution of the REINFORCING objectives and work plan. The REINFORCING Consortium commits to handling personal data confidentiality except for the call results, which will contain the following information:

- Information about successful REINFORCING funding support applications that will be made publicly available before the end of the project containing project title, names of project partners and short project description (as provided by the applicant in the application template).
- Information about successful REINFORCING funding support that will be made publicly available after the end of the project: project title, names of project partners, awarded funding and updated short project description (as provided by the project partners in the Final Report).

The processing of data that REINFORCING Consortium intends to carry out will be based on lawfulness and correctness in the full protection of its rights and its confidentiality pursuant to the general principles of the GDPR and its art.24. Therefore, the competitors are informed of the procedure that the data provided by the applicants will be treated exclusively with reference to the procedure for which they submitted the documentation.

The applicants can exercise their rights towards the data controller, pursuant to article 12 of the GDPR. For any inquiries regarding the processing of your personal data, please read more about the privacy policy of the entity in charge of REINFORCING grantees' contracts management, Consorzio Italbiotec, that can be downloaded directly from the project website. Application selection and evaluation will be performed under the appropriate ethical conduct and will respect the confidentiality of the information received.

7 DISCLAIMER

- **Purpose:** This text is explaining the REINFORCING financial support scheme for information purposes only. No rights can be claimed on the basis of this document. This document does not reflect the views of the European Commission and REA.
- **Mistakes or inconsistencies:** The REINFORCING Consortium is not responsible for any mistakes or misinterpretations that this text may cause. In the case of inconsistencies, the Consortium will determine the steps to be taken, in cooperation with the applicant concerned.
- **Modification of the Terms and Conditions:** The REINFORCING partners, represented by the coordinator, are entitled to modify these Terms and Conditions (including re-opening/closing dates of the calls, in case of non-granting of funds and/or early depletion of the available funds, or as they see fit) at any time without notice. The current Guide for Applicants will be provided on the project website (www.reinforcing.eu) always mentioning the version number. The most recent version of the Terms and Conditions of the REINFORCING financial support scheme applies and prevails.
- **Consequential damages:** In no event shall either party be liable to the other or any of its affiliates for any consequential, incidental, indirect, special, punitive or exemplary damages (including, without limitation, lost profits, business or goodwill) suffered or incurred by such other party or its affiliates in connection with this financial support scheme, even if advised of the possibility of such damages.

8 SUPPORT TO APPLICANTS

Additional information is provided in the FAQ (Annex 4) published on the project website.

For further information on the call or if you have any doubts relating to the eligibility rules or the information that is to be provided in the Application form, please contact the Support Team: grants@reinforcing.eu

ANNEX 1 – ORRI BOOSTER TEMPLATE

Instructions to complete the template

The structure of this template must be followed when preparing your proposal for **ORRI Booster Grants**. It has been designed to ensure that the important aspects of your planned work are presented in a way that will enable the evaluators to make an adequate assessment against the evaluation criteria. Please be aware that proposals will be evaluated as they were submitted rather than on their potential if certain changes were to be made.

The page limit for full proposals is **5 pages** (excluding section 1, section 2, budget tables). Please do not consider the page limit as a target. It is in your interest to keep your text as concise as possible since the evaluators will not view unnecessarily long proposals in a positive light.

The minimum font size allowed is 11 points. Standard character spacing and a minimum of single-line spacing are to be used. This applies to the body text, including text in tables. The page size is A4, and all margins (top, bottom, left, right) should be at least 15 mm (not including any footers or headers).

General guidance for applicants:

- The proposal must be submitted in English
- The proposal is structured as follows:
 - Online form to be completed (see section 1 of the present template)
 - Proposal template to be uploaded in a pdf format (from section 2 of the present template)
 - Declaration of Honour to be uploaded in a pdf format. Each partner must complete and sign the declaration of honour independently (one file for each partner).
- Any documents other than those requested as part of the proposal will not be taken into account during the evaluation

Please delete this page when submitting the proposal. Instructions can be deleted as well. Please also remove section 1, which will be completed in an online form.

1. GENERAL INFORMATION

[This section will be completed online; remove section 1 before submitting the application]

Acronym of the proposal	
Full title of the proposal	
Duration (in months)	
Number of project partners	

Country of project partners	
ORRI keywords	<p><i>Choose from the list + 2 free keywords maximum (free keywords are optional)</i></p> <p><i>RRI</i> <i>Open Innovation (including Citizen Innovation)</i> <i>Open Science (including Citizen Science)</i> <i>Societal Engagement (including Citizen Engagement and Co-creation)</i> <i>Anticipatory governance</i> <i>Sustainability</i> <i>Ethics (including Bioethics, AI Ethics, and Research Ethics)</i> <i>Diversity, Equity and Inclusion</i></p>
Challenge to be addressed (50 words max)	<i>(What kind of challenge do you want to address thanks to the Open Responsible Research and Innovation approach? (1 paragraph))</i>
Changes to be achieved by the project (50 words max)	<i>(What kind of changes are you aiming to achieve with your project?)</i>
Date of submission	
Abstract (300 words max)	

2. ADMINISTRATIVE INFORMATION

[The following paragraphs must be completed on this template. You will be asked to upload this template in a pdf format on the REINFORCING project website]

2.1 List of participating organization(s)

#	Organization full name	Short name	Country
1			
2			

[Remove or add rows depending on the number of partners]

2.2 Data of the participating organization(s)

Lead Partner	
Legal Name (and short name)	
Type of legal entity	
Address of the organization	Street name and number: Town: Postal code:
Country	
VAT number (optional)	
PIC¹ (optional)	
Website of the organization	
Social media channels (optional)	LinkedIn: X (former Twitter):
Main contact person	Name: Surname: Position in the organization: E-mail address: Phone number: ORCID (optional):
Legal representative (if different from the primary contact person)	Name: Surname: E-mail address: Phone number:
Past achievements and projects	
[List up to 5 achievements and projects relevant to the call topic]	

¹<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/participant-register>

Does the organization have a Gender Equality Plan in line with the requests of the Horizon Europe Programme ² ? (Yes/No; if yes, add the link to the GEP)	
Have you received other funding related to REINFORCING cascading grants? (Yes/No) If yes, please indicate the full name and acronym of the proposal and the financing you received	

[Repeat the above table for the other partners (if any)]

3. OBJECTIVES, NEEDS and APPROACH [Excellence]

3.1 Objectives

Describe the objectives of your proposal and how they are aligned with the call requirements.

Objectives should be realistic and measurable.

3.2 Needs and proposed approach to address them

Describe the needs you would like to address, the main potential challenges and how you plan to address them in relation to the project’s objectives, highlighting the ORRI approach.

3.2.1 Gender³

Describe how you plan to consider Gender practices (ideally enlarging them toward Diversity, Equity and Inclusivity) when implementing the project

3.2.2 Open science⁴

Describe how you plan to include Open Science practices within your proposed actions

3.3. Previous experience in ORRI

²<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ffcb06c3-200a-11ec-bd8e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-232129669>

³<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ffcb06c3-200a-11ec-bd8e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-232129669>; https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/democracy-and-rights/gender-equality-research-and-innovation_en

⁴https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

[D4.2-[REINFORCING cascading grants supporting Documents - Guidelines for applicants]]

Describe your previous experience in ORRI and how the proposal aims to contribute to strengthening and institutionalizing the ORRI approach

4. CHANGES TO BE ACHIEVED [Impact]

Describe the changes you want to achieve with your project, referring to potential benefits for your organization(s) and society at large.

5. ACTIVITIES [Implementation]

5.1 Work Plan

Describe how you plan to implement your activities in order to achieve the planned objectives and the expected changes. Insert a graphical flow-chart (e.g. GANTT or similar) showing the project timeline per actions as identified below.

Divide your work plan into Actions (A). For each action, state the objectives, describe the activities, and list the expected milestones and the expected results (be as quantitative as possible when listing the results).

Action 1 – Title of the action	
Lead partner	
Duration (in months)	Start month – end month
Objectives of the action	
Description of the action	
Expected results	

[Copy the above structure for all the planned actions]

5.2 Budget

For general eligibility conditions related to costs and budget categories, please see article 6 of the [Horizon Europe AGA \(V1.0 DRAFT – 01.04-2023\)](#).

Eligible costs include:

[D4.2-[REINFORCING cascading grants supporting Documents - Guidelines for applicants]]

Personnel costs as described in Article 6.2.A of the Horizon Europe Annotated Grant Agreement (AGA).

Purchase costs include:

Other goods, works or services, if necessary to implement the action (see Article 6.2.C.3 of the Horizon Europe AGA).

Indirect costs (or overheads) are costs that cannot be identified as specific costs directly linked to the performance of the action. To be calculated as a 25% flat rate of the eligible direct costs (personnel costs and purchase costs).

Partner Name	Personnel Costs	Purchase costs	Overheads	Total
Partner 1				
Partner 2				
Partner ..				
Total				

For each partner, please provide more details for each category:

Personnel costs: how many people do you plan to involve in the action? What is their level of expertise? For how many hours? (e.g. we plan to work with 2 junior researchers at 50% of their time and 1 senior researcher at 30% of his time)

Purchase costs: make a list of the costs included in this category.

ANNEX 2 – ORRI INCUBATOR TEMPLATE

Instructions to complete the template

The structure of this template must be followed when preparing your proposal for **ORRI Incubator Grants**. It has been designed to ensure that the important aspects of your planned work are presented in a way that will enable the evaluators to make an adequate assessment against the evaluation criteria. Please be aware that proposals will be evaluated as they were submitted rather than on their potential if certain changes were to be made.

The page limit for full proposals is **10 pages** (excluding section 1, section 2, budget tables and annexes). Please do not consider the page limit as a target. It is in your interest to keep your text as concise as possible since the evaluators will not view unnecessarily long proposals in a positive light.

The minimum font size allowed is 11 points. Standard character spacing and a minimum of single-line spacing are to be used. This applies to the body text, including text in tables. The page size is A4, and all margins (top, bottom, left, right) should be at least 15 mm (not including any footers or headers).

General guidance for applicants:

- The proposal must be submitted in English
- The proposal is structured as follows:
 - Online form to be completed (see section 1 of the present template)
 - Proposal template to be uploaded in a pdf format (from section 2 of the present template)
 - Declaration of Honour to be uploaded in a pdf format. Each partner must complete and sign the declaration of honour independently (one file for each partner).
- Any documents other than those requested as part of the proposal will not be taken into account during the evaluation

Please delete this page when submitting the proposal. Instructions can be deleted as well. Please also remove section 1, which will be completed in an online form.

1. GENERAL INFORMATION

[This section will be completed online; remove section 1 before submitting the application]

Acronym of the proposal	
Full title of the proposal	
Duration (in months)	
Number of project partners	
Country of project partners	

ORRI keywords	<p><i>Choose from the list + 2 free keywords maximum (free keywords are optional)</i></p> <p><i>RRI</i> <i>Open Innovation (including Citizen Innovation)</i> <i>Open Science (including Citizen Science)</i> <i>Societal Engagement (including Citizen Engagement and Co-creation)</i> <i>Anticipatory governance</i> <i>Sustainability</i> <i>Ethics (including Bioethics, AI Ethics, and Research Ethics)</i> <i>Diversity, Equity and Inclusion</i></p>
Challenge to be addressed (50 words max)	<i>(What kind of challenge do you want to address thanks to the Open Responsible Research and Innovation approach? (1 paragraph))</i>
Changes to be achieved by the project (50 words max)	<i>(What kind of changes are you aiming to achieve with your project?)</i>
Date of submission	
Abstract (300 words max)	

2. ADMINISTRATIVE INFORMATION

[The following paragraphs must be completed on this template. You will be asked to upload this template in a pdf format on the REINFORCING project website]

2.1 List of participating organization(s)

#	Organization full name	Short name	Country
1			
2			

[Remove or add rows depending on the number of partners]

2.2 Data of the participating organization(s)

Lead Partner	
Legal Name (and short name)	

Type of legal entity	
Address of the organization	Street name and number: Town: Postal code:
Country	
VAT number (optional)	
PIC⁵ (optional)	
Website of the organization	
Social media channels (optional)	LinkedIn: X (former Twitter):
Main contact person	Name: Surname: Position in the organization: E-mail address: Phone number: ORCID (optional):
Legal representative (if different from the primary contact person)	Name: Surname: E-mail address: Phone number:
Does the organization have a Gender Equality Plan in line with the requests of the Horizon Europe Programme ⁶ ? (Yes/No; if yes, add the link to the GEP)	
Have you received other funding related to REINFORCING cascading grants? (Yes/No) If yes, please indicate the full name and acronym of the proposal and the financing you received	

[Repeat the above table for the other partners (if any)]

⁵<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/participant-register>

⁶<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ffcb06c3-200a-11ec-bd8e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-232129669>

3. OBJECTIVES, NEEDS and APPROACH [Excellence]

3.1 Objectives

Describe the objectives of your proposal and how they are aligned with the call requirements.

Objectives should be realistic and measurable.

3.2 Needs and proposed approach to address them

Describe the needs you would like to address, the main potential challenges and how you plan to address them in relation to the project's objectives, highlighting the ORRI approach.

3.2.1 Gender⁷

Describe how you plan to consider Gender practices (ideally enlarging them toward Diversity, Equity and Inclusivity) when implementing the project

3.2.2 Open science⁸

Describe how you plan to include Open Science practices within your proposed actions

4. CHANGES TO BE ACHIEVED [Impact]

Describe the changes you want to achieve with your project, referring to potential benefits for your organization(s) and society at large.

5. ACTIVITIES [Implementation]

5.1 Work Plan

Describe how you plan to implement your activities in order to achieve the planned objectives and the expected changes. Insert a graphical flow-chart (e.g. GANTT or similar) showing the project timeline per actions as identified below.

Divide your work plan into Actions (A). For each action, state the objectives, describe the activities, and list the expected milestones and the expected results (be as quantitative as possible when listing the results). When describing each action, you can foresee sub-activities called Tasks (T).

Action 1 – Title of the action	
Lead partner	
Duration (in months)	Start month – end month
Objectives of the action	

⁷<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ffcb06c3-200a-11ec-bd8e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-232129669>; https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/democracy-and-rights/gender-equality-research-and-innovation_en

⁸https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

<p>Description of the action</p> <p>Task 1.1 – title of the task (start month – end month)</p>
<p>Expected results</p>
<p>Milestones</p> <p><i>e.g. organization of a workshop, preparation of some guidelines etc. For each milestone, identify a title and include a brief description and the deadline for reaching the milestone.</i></p>

[Copy the above structure for all the planned actions]

5.2 Description of the consortium

Describe the consortium and how the collaboration between partners will help address the objectives of the project. Describe how the members complement one another and in what way each of them contributes to the project.

5.3 Budget

For general eligibility conditions related to costs and budget categories, please see article 6 of the [Horizon Europe AGA \(V1.0 DRAFT – 01.04-2023\)](#).

Eligible costs include:

Personnel costs as described in Article 6.2.A of the Horizon Europe Annotated Grant Agreement (AGA).

Purchase costs include:

Travel, accommodation and subsistence (see Article 6.2.C.1 of the Horizon Europe AGA)

Other goods, works or services, if necessary to implement the action (see Article 6.2.C.3 of the Horizon Europe AGA).

Indirect costs (or overheads) are costs that cannot be identified as specific costs directly linked to the performance of the action. To be calculated as a 25% flat rate of the eligible direct costs (personnel costs and purchase costs).

Partner Name	Personnel Costs	Purchase costs	Overheads	Total
--------------	-----------------	----------------	-----------	-------

Partner 1				
Partner 2				
Partner ..				
Total				

For each partner, please provide more details for each category:

Personnel costs: how many people do you plan to involve in the action? What is their level of expertise? For how many hours? (e.g. we plan to work with 2 junior researchers at 50% of their time and 1 senior researcher at 30% of his time)

Purchase costs: make a list of the costs included in this category.

ANNEX 3 – DECLARATION OF HONOUR

[The present annex must be completed and (preferably in digital format) signed by each applicant. The signed document(s) must be uploaded together with the Technical Application Form on the project website. Please delete the instructions before signing and submitting the document.]

Declaration of honour – [INSERT HERE THE ACRONYM OF THE PROPOSAL]

The undersigned:

<i>(only for natural persons)</i> themselves	<i>(only for legal persons)</i> the following legal person:
<i>(for legal persons)</i> [Insert here the name of the legal signatory] representing:	Full name of the organization: Organization address: Country: VAT registration number:

Confirms that:

The information provided for the proposal [*insert here the full name and acronym of the proposal*] is correct and complete;

Complies with the eligibility criteria and all other conditions set out in the call for the entire duration of the action;

Is not subject to a conflict of interest in connection with this grant and will notify, without delay, any situation which could give rise to a conflict of interest;

Fully accepts all REINFORCING conditions and rules as detailed in the REINFORCING Guide for Applicants and in the specific REINFORCING call text.

Declares that I/my organization:

Is committed to participating in the action;

has stable and sufficient sources of funding to maintain the activities throughout the checking action and to provide any counterpart funding necessary;

Has or will have the necessary financial and staff resources to implement the action.

Declares that it is NOT in one of the following situations:

It is subject to an administrative sanction (i.e. exclusion or financial penalty decision);

It is bankrupt, being wound up, having the affairs administered by the courts, entering into an arrangement with creditors, suspended business activities or subject to any other similar proceedings or procedures;

It is in breach of social security or tax obligations;

It has been guilty of grave professional misconduct;

It has committed fraud, corruption, links to a criminal organisation, money laundering, terrorism-related crimes (including terrorism financing), child labour or human trafficking;

It has shown significant deficiencies in complying with main obligations under any procurement procedures, grant agreement, prize, expert contract, or similar guilty of irregularities.

Commits to pursue REINFORCING objectives and in particular:

Deliver at least one tool to be included in the REINFORCING project online platform;

Contribute to updating the REINFORCING project online platform with grantees' achievements and information;

Attend a final webinar in which grantees will be asked to present their results;

Participate in a mid-term review online meeting to assess the impact of the grants on my organization;

[Only for ORRI Incubators (large grants). Remove if ORRI Boosters (small grants)]
Attends preliminary on-site ORRI training of at least one day and a half at the beginning of activities (likely in Brussels).

I/my organization confirms that:

[*choose the correct one*] has no significant expertise in the ORRI field and would like to embark on an ORRI approach [OR] is already experienced in ORRI and would like to strengthen/institutionalize their ORRI approach;

has not sent other applications for the same call;

[*choose the correct one*] has not received other funding related to REINFORCING cascading grants [OR] has received additional funding related to REINFORCING cascading grants and is aware the funding amount received by the same organization doesn't exceed €60 000.

I/my organisation is aware that false declarations may lead to rejection, suspension, termination or reduction of the grant.

I/my organization acknowledges that all proposals and related data, knowledge and documents will be treated according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016).

Date:

Name of the legal signatory:

Signature:

ANNEX 4 – FREQUANTLY ASKED QUESTIONS

1. SUBMISSION AND EVALUATION PROCESS

1.1 Where can I find the calls published by REINFORCING?

The REINFORCING calls are published on the [Funding & Tenders portal](#).

The direct link to each call text and supporting documentation can be found on the REINFORCING project website: <https://www.reinforcing.eu/open-calls/open-calls>

1.2 Which supporting documents are available for applicants?

Besides the call text, the following documents are available for applicants:

- Guide for applicants.
- Frequently asked questions on REINFORCING cascading grants (this document you are reading).
- Template for the submission (two different templates based on the type of call you are applying to).
- Template for the Declaration of Honour

Check the project website (<https://www.reinforcing.eu/open-calls/open-calls>) to download this material.

Furthermore, webinars for applicants – with a Q&A slot - will be organized for each launch of the seven REINFORCING calls. The recording will be available on the project website.

1.3 How can I submit my proposal? Is it possible to send it to the REINFORCING consortium by email?

Unless otherwise indicated in the specific text of the call, all applications must be sent via the dedicated REINFORCING webpage (<https://www.reinforcing.eu/open-calls/open-calls>). Applications received by any other means (e.g. email) and after the call deadline will not be accepted.

1.4 How many calls are foreseen?

The REINFORCING project will publish seven calls starting from November 2023 until December 2025, of which four ORRI Booster grants (small) and three ORRI Incubator grants (large).

Small grants, also called **ORRI boosters**, will be awarded to applicants already experienced in ORRI that would like to strengthen and institutionalize their ORRI approach. Each ORRI boosters project will last 8 months and can be awarded a maximum of 20,000 €.

Large grants, also called **ORRI incubators**, will be awarded to consortia of beneficiaries (at least two beneficiaries per consortium) that are newcomers in ORRI and that would like to embark on an ORRI approach. Each ORRI incubators project will last 12 months and can be awarded a maximum of 60.000 €.

For more information, read the Guide for Applicants that can be downloaded from our project website: <https://www.reinforcing.eu/open-calls/open-calls>.

1.5 How can I prove that my organization is financially stable?

Each applicant will be asked to declare their financial stability by signing the Declaration of Honour. No supporting documents are needed. However, please be aware that false declarations may lead to rejection, suspension, termination or reduction of the grant.

1.6 How long should the proposal's text be?

The page limit is indicated in the template for the application. Proposals shorter than the page limit will be accepted, whilst proposals exceeding the page limit will be rejected. It is in your interest to keep your text as concise as possible since the evaluators will not view unnecessarily long proposals in a positive light.

1.7 Would it be advisable to attach letters of support?

No, you are only requested to upload the proposal template and the signed Declaration of Honour. Any other documents will not be taken into account

2. ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

2.1 Which type of organisations can apply for REINFORCING cascading grants?

All types of organizations can apply for REINFORCING cascading grants if they comply with the eligibility criteria reported in the Guide for Applicants.

2.2 Can consortia also apply for ORRI Booster grants (small grants)?

Yes, it is possible for consortia of two or more beneficiaries to apply for ORRI Booster grants (small grants), provided that they do not request more than 20,000 € in total.

2.3 Is it possible to send multiple applications for the same call?

No, it is not possible. If an organisation sends more than one application for the same call, such an organisation will be automatically excluded from the evaluation.

2.4 Is applying for other calls under the REINFORCING cascading grants scheme possible?

Yes, it is possible as long as the funding amount received by the same organisation doesn't exceed €60.000

2.5 I represent an entity not based in Europe. Can I apply?

To be eligible for funding, applicants must be established in one of the following countries:

- the Member States of the European Union, including their outermost regions
- the Overseas Countries and Territories (OCTs) linked to the Member States
- countries associated with Horizon Europe

[D4.2-[REINFORCING cascading grants supporting Documents - Guidelines for applicants]]

low- and middle-income countries as listed in the [General Annexes of the Horizon Europe Work Programme 2023-2024](#).

Legal entities established in countries not listed above will not be eligible for funding under the REINFORCING grants.

For more details, see the section “Entities eligible for funding” of the [General Annexes of the Horizon Europe Work Programme 2023-2024](#).

2.6 I submitted a proposal in a REINFORCING call, but I was unsuccessful. May I submit a new proposal in the next call?

Yes, you can apply again to another REINFORCING call provided that the topic fits your proposal and the activities align with the general criteria as detailed in the general criteria. However, if you were excluded from the first call because your organization didn't fit the eligibility criteria, your organization will not be able to apply again anyway.

2.7 What does the REINFORCING consortium mean for “Conflict of interest”?

A conflict of Interest (CoI) can occur when your organization is directly linked to a REINFORCING partner (i.e. working in a different department/unit of the same institution, which is a REINFORCING partner). Still, other cases can be considered as CoI. EU Commission conflict of interests rules apply, and you can find more info on there [here](#).

2.8 Which costs are eligible under REINFORCING cascading grants?

For general eligibility conditions related to costs and budget categories, please see Article 6 of the [Horizon Europe AGA \(V1.0 DRAFT – 01.04-2023\)](#).

Eligible costs include:

- Personnel costs as described in Article in 6.2.A of the Horizon Europe AGA.
- Purchase costs include:
 - Travel, accommodation and subsistence (see Article 6.2.C.1 of the Horizon Europe AGA) – **only for ORRI Incubators (large grants)**
 - Other goods, works, or services, if necessary, to implement the action (see Article 6.2.C.3 of the Horizon Europe AGA).
- Indirect costs (or overheads) cannot be identified as specific costs directly linked to the performance of the action. They are calculate as a 25% flat rate of the eligible direct costs (personnel costs and purchase costs).

2.9 Can the REINFORCING budget be integrated with other funds?

REINFORCING grants are expected to fund 100% of the budget of the action. The maximum budget that can be requested for each type of call is expected to cover the REINFORCING objectives and call requests fully. However, applicants may include REINFORCING grants in a more extensive plan towards institutional changes. In this context, it is essential to bear in mind that no double funding is allowed, which means that no costs for the same activity can be funded twice.

3. PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 My proposal was successful. When will the funding arrive?

All grantees will receive pre-financing at the beginning of the project, namely, ten days before the project starts. The pre-financing amount depends on the grant type (50% for ORRI Booster and 40% for ORRI Incubators). The remaining amount will be distributed concurrently to the validation of Progress Reports (one for ORRI Booster and two for ORRI Incubators) to avoid misuse of funds. For more details, check the Guide for Applicants that can be downloaded from our website: <https://www.reinforcing.eu/open-calls/open-calls> .

3.2 What information will be required in the Progress Reports?

The Progress Reports will include a detailed description of the implemented activities, the justifications for expenses, the problems encountered, and the solutions adopted according to the template provided by the contracting entity.

3.3 Do beneficiaries need to provide additional information/documents than the Progress Reports?

No, you are only required to submit Progress Reports in a timely manner according to the template provided by the contracting entity. However, you must - at least for three years after the final payment — keep records and other supporting documents to prove the proper implementation of the action and the incurred costs.

Furthermore, at the end of the project, you will be required to provide a concrete output to be included in the REINFORCING One-Stop Source.

3.4 Do beneficiaries have other obligations than reporting their activities? Are there other activities in which they will be engaged within the frame of REINFORCING?

REINFORCING beneficiaries will be asked to:

- Deliver at least one ORRI tool to be included in the REINFORCING One-Stop Source, the EU central virtual platform on ORRI that REINFORCING is developing;
- Contribute to update the REINFORCING project website with grantees' achievements and information;
- Attend and contribute to a final webinar in which grantees will be asked to present their results;
- Participate in a mid-term review meeting aimed to assess the impact of the grants on beneficiaries;
- (*Only for ORRI Incubators*) Attend preliminary training activities at the beginning of project activities to familiarize with ORRI principles. Training will last one day and a half on-site in Brussels. Costs related to training (personnel and travel) can be funded by the grant (thus to be included in the budget overview).
- (*Suggested but not mandatory*) Promote project activities and EU funding through REINFORCING on online channels (webpage on partners' website; social media communication).

4. OTHERS

4.1 What can I do if I have further questions not included in the Guide for Applicants or FAQs?

For further information on the call or if you have any doubts about eligibility rules or the information to be provided in the Application form, please contact the Support Team at grants@reinforcing.eu.

4.2 Does REINFORCING fund research and innovation projects?

No, REINFORCING grants are aimed at supporting activities to implement ORRI processes. Thus, they do not fund:

- Research project to only produce academic results
- Innovation projects in terms of development of a product or a process
- Research projects on ORRI (e.g. investigate ORRI from a theoretical point of view)